

Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability

Deliverable 10.6 - AtlantECO policy briefs

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	Diana Sousa (SPI)	Initial draft	07.08.2025
0.2	Diana Sousa (SPI)	Added content and updated sections	14.10.2025
0.3	Diana Sousa, Elisa Frias-Bulhosa, Raquel Silva	Content revision and additional contributions	17.11.2025
0.4	Raquel Silva (SPI)	Inclusion of policy brief #4	06.02.2026
0.5	Stéphane Pesant (EMBL-EBI)	Inclusion of policy brief #2	24.02.2026
0.6	Diana Sousa (SPI)	Final internal review and revision	25.02.2026
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2 Executive summary

This deliverable presents the AtlantECO policy briefs, developed under *Task 10.3 - Contribution to EU Marine Strategy and Policy*, which aim to translate scientific results into actionable recommendations for sustainable management and governance of the Atlantic Ocean. Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI) is the main responsible for the production of the briefs, with key contributions from consortium partners.

The document presents a set of four policy briefs addressing key challenges in transatlantic research cooperation, ocean microbiome genetic resources, the Blue Economy, and projects clustering across HorizonEU Work Programmes, providing guidance for policymakers, stakeholders, and the broader scientific community. It builds upon previous technical tasks and integrates the project's latest outputs, lessons learned, and emerging opportunities to strengthen transatlantic cooperation, equitable access to marine resources, and the integration of science into policy.

The briefs focus on four strategic areas: (1) **Advancing Equitable Research Cooperation**, promoting fair and inclusive North–South partnerships; (2) **The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource**, supporting equitable access and benefit-sharing; (3) **Blue Economy and Nature-based Solutions**, aligning scientific innovation with sustainable marine policy and economic development; and (4) **Impact for Clustering** across Horizon work programmes.

Dissemination and engagement were supported through open-access publication on Zenodo platform, presentations at conferences, meetings and events in Europe, Brazil, and South Africa, targeting policymakers, international organizations, marine agencies, academia, civil society, and industry. These actions ensure AtlantECO's knowledge outputs inform EU and international marine strategies, foster dialogue across the All-Atlantic Ocean Research Community, and support the long-term sustainability and impact of the project's recommendations.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

As part of its mission to develop and apply a novel, unifying framework for the understanding and management of the Atlantic Ocean and its ecosystem services, the AtlantECO project has produced a set of policy briefs. These briefs serve as key knowledge translation tools, aiming to connect AtlantECO 's priority research areas with concrete, actionable policy recommendations. Their purpose is to support the sustainable use, protection, and equitable governance of marine ecosystems across the Atlantic basin.

AtlantECO aims to develop and implement a novel, unifying framework for observing and managing Atlantic marine ecosystems. The project brings together experts and institutions from Europe, South America, and South Africa to integrate multidisciplinary research on three foundational pillars: **marine microbiomes**, **marine plastic pollution and the plastisphere**, and **seascape connectivity**. It also seeks to engage with citizens and actors from the industry and policy sectors to stimulate responsible behaviour and Blue Growth.

In alignment with its objectives to engage with decision-makers, promote co-design of knowledge, and support science-policy-society interfaces, the project developed four targeted and accessible policy briefs to inform those shaping the future of the Atlantic Ocean.

3.1 Objectives and purpose of the policy briefs

The AtlantECO policy briefs were developed to:

- **To distil complex scientific language** into concise and targeted messages relevant for policy and decision-making;
- **Support policy frameworks**, such as EU's Green Deal, the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters, the Biodiversity Strategy 2030, and the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance;
- **Promote transatlantic cooperation**, inclusive participation, and knowledge-sharing across diverse ocean governance frameworks;
- **Encourage uptake and implementation** of AtlantECO's key findings and outcomes, such as the role of the ocean microbiome in ecosystem health, the importance of seascape-scale observation, and the integration of nature-based solutions into the blue economy.

These policy briefs also contribute to the legacy and impact pathways of AtlantECO by providing tools that can be used beyond the project's lifespan to support evidence-based decision-making and capacity building.

3.2 Overview of the Policy Briefs

The four policy briefs developed under AtlantECO focus on strategically selected themes that reflect major areas of relevance to the project and its contribution to international marine science-policy dialogues.

Policy brief #1 -Advancing Equitable Research Cooperation in Ocean Sciences across the Atlantic Ocean

This brief addresses the need for fair, inclusive, and balanced transatlantic collaboration in ocean research. It explores barriers and opportunities to strengthen partnerships, particularly between countries in the North and South Atlantic. The brief highlights actions to support capacity development, data sharing, funding opportunities and long-term institutional cooperation.

Policy brief #2 - The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource: Equitable access and shared capacity for the benefit of One Ocean, One Health

This policy brief summarises the concepts, scope, and current use of digital sequence information about the Ocean Microbiome genetic resources collected in exclusive economic zones and in high seas beyond national jurisdiction. It calls for equitable access and shared capacity, and proposes methods to monitor and report on access and benefits from marine digital sequence information.

Policy brief #3 - Blue Economy and Nature-based Solutions: A Sustainable Future for Atlantic Industries

The policy brief calls for stronger alignment between scientific innovation and marine policy to advance a Sustainable Blue Economy across Europe, Africa, and South America. It emphasizes the need for better integration of science into policy, particularly in leveraging marine microbiomes for environmental restoration and economic opportunities.

Policy brief #4 - Clustering for Impact: Lessons learned from #AllAtlantic Cluster - Recommendations to EC REA and future Horizon EU & FP10 applicants on strategies and mechanisms for agile clustering of parallel project portfolios

The policy brief is a collaborative output of **Mission Atlantic** (<https://missionatlantic.eu/>) and **AtlantECO** projects. The Policy Brief is a direct product of the two project managers in 2021-2024 running the All-Atlantic CLUSTER of projects under the same Flagship Portfolio. This document delivers recommendations both for applicants and funders.

3.3 Methodology

The policy briefs were developed through a multi-step, participatory process that ensured scientific robustness, stakeholder relevance, and policy alignment:

- Thematic scoping based on AtlantECO's areas of interest and scientific outputs;
- Consultation with partners to identify priority issues and relevant policy frameworks;
- Drafting and internal review led by partners with expertise in ocean science and governance;
- Design and dissemination through multiple project communication channels, international events, and tailored outreach efforts.

This process ensured that the briefs reflect the transdisciplinary nature of AtlantECO and are grounded in both scientific evidence and policy relevance.

3.4 Target Audiences

The AtlantECO policy briefs are designed to inform and engage a diverse range of stakeholders involved in ocean governance, scientific research, and sustainable development. The key target groups are described below:

Table 1- AtlantECO policy briefs' target groups

Target Audience	Description	Purpose of Engagement
European and International Policymakers	European Commission services, international bodies, regional ocean governance platforms	Inform policy design and support alignment with EU and global marine and climate strategies
National and Regional Authorities	Ministries of environment, science, fisheries and maritime affairs, coastal municipalities and regional blue economy clusters	Support implementation of project-relevant policies and alignment with national ocean and innovation strategies

Scientific and Innovation Community	Universities, marine research institutions, marine biotech companies, and innovation platforms	Encourage uptake of AtlantECO science, support co-design of future research agendas, and promote science-policy dialogue
Civil Society and Advocacy Network	Environmental NGOs, community-based organisations, citizen science groups	Build broader support for project outcomes and increase public awareness of ocean health and equity issues

3.5 Dissemination

All four AtlantECO policy briefs have been published and made openly accessible via **Zenodo**, ensuring their long-term availability and facilitating citation and reuse by the scientific, policy, and civil society communities. The documents can be accessed at:

Table 2- Publication details and engagement metrics for AtlantECO policy briefs

Policy brief	Hyperlink	Publication Date	Metrics
Policy brief #1 - Advancing equitable research cooperation in Ocean sciences across the Atlantic Ocean	https://zenodo.org/records/14989171	7 March 2025	172 views 174 downloads
Policy brief #2 - The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource: Equitable access and shared capacity for the benefit of One Ocean, One Health	https://zenodo.org/records/18771618	25 February 2026	6 views 1 download
Policy brief #3 - Blue Economy and nature-based solutions: A sustainable future for Atlantic Industries	https://zenodo.org/records/17914958	12 December 2025	62 views 41 downloads
Policy brief #4 - Clustering for Impact: Lessons learned from #AllAtlantic Cluster	https://zenodo.org/records/18507114	30 September 2024	351 views 259 downloads

To maximize their impact, the policy briefs have been disseminated through:

- Presentation at policy-oriented events, such as All-Atlantic conferences, UN Ocean Decade, and European Ocean Days;
- Roundtables and direct outreach to policy officers and ministries in Atlantic countries;
- Inclusion in project communication channels, such as newsletters, social media, and the AtlantECO website;
- Engagement with relevant stakeholder networks through the AtlantECO policy roadshow.

The dissemination strategy combined physical distribution, digital access (via QR codes and web platforms), participation in scientific sessions, and policy-oriented dialogues.

The table below summarises the main dissemination activities undertaken during the AtlantECO Policy Roadshow.

Table 3- AtlantECO policy roadshow

Event	Date & Location	Format	Description
All-Atlantic Marine Ecosystems: A Science to Policy event	3 Oct 2022 Lisbon, Portugal	In-person	The European funded projects AtlantECO, Mission Atlantic, and AANChOR co-organized a science-to-policy debate in the framework of the TARA Microbiomes flagship mission that docked in Portugal. This science-to-policy debate was developed under the framework of the AAORIA and aimed to disseminate relevant marine ecosystem knowledge in scope of the project activities that supported the European and international ocean governance agenda. The event gathered scientists and policy experts to discuss and shed light on related capacity building and infrastructure capacity needs and solutions in scope of the Atlantic marine cooperation.
10 years of the Galway Statement	5-6 July 2023 Galway, Ireland	In-person	AtlantECO attended the event represented by Stéphane Pesant. An event co-organised by the Irish Government, the European Commission, the Marine Institute, and the University of Galway, bringing together European and international Atlantic partners and actors.
Atlantic Ocean: Connecting People and Science	5 Oct 2023 Florianopolis , Brazil	In-person	Along with the project Mission Atlantic, Brazilian policymakers and decision-makers from the Ministry of Science and Technology and other Government institutions were present at the session engaging in discussions with researchers.
All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance Forum 2023	21-22 Nov 2023 Cape Town, South Africa	In-person	Presentation showcasing the project's work on equity, diversity, inclusion, and capacity building in Atlantic research cooperation. The contribution highlighted AtlantECO's recommendations for strengthening North-South collaboration, supporting staff-exchange initiatives, and fostering shared policy dialogue across the Atlantic.
European Ocean Days 2025	3-7 Mar 2025 Brussels, Belgium	In-person	Dissemination of Policy brief #1 - Advancing Equitable Research Cooperation in Ocean Sciences Across the Atlantic Ocean . 25 printed copies were distributed and 100 QR-code cards shared with the event participants.
One Ocean Science Congress	3-6 Jun 2025 Nice, France	In-person	Scientific talk by Stéphane Pesant, presenting Policy Brief #2 – The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource: Equitable Access and Shared Capacity for the Benefit of One Ocean, One Health . Abstract available here .
UN Ocean Conference	9-13 Jun 2025 Nice, France	In-person	AtlantECO featured in two talks during the event (OOS2025-688 & OOS2025-1340), titled "New genetic resources collected during the Mission Microbiomes in the Atlantic" and "Equitable access to ocean microbiome genetic resources". Both presentations aligned with the messages of Policy brief #1 - Advancing Equitable Research Cooperation in Ocean Sciences Across the Atlantic Ocean , and Policy Brief #2 – The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource: Equitable Access and Shared Capacity for the Benefit of One Ocean, One Health .
Policy Meeting - Brazilian Ministry of Environment (MMA)	7 August 2025 Brasília, Brazil	In-person	Meeting at the MMA to present the AtlantECO Mission Microbiomes and explore its interfaces with Brazilian public policies, with a particular focus on marine genetic resources, MGRs, and the implementation of the BBNJ Agreement. The mission's scope and methodological design, including its Atlantic sampling strategy, integration of multi omics data, and planned scientific and policy outputs, were outlined together with initial findings and potential applications for marine monitoring and evidence-based management. Discussions also

			addressed key governance dimensions, including data access and sharing frameworks, as well as benefit sharing mechanisms related to MGRs. Participants included representatives from MMA, the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, MCTI, the Brazilian Navy, the Tara Ocean Foundation, and UFSCar.
AtlantECO Final Conference - Session “From Atlantic Cooperation to Global Ocean Policy”	15-19 Sept 2025 Ponta Delgada, Portugal	In-person	On the day dedicated to ocean policy, the event brought together key stakeholders from across the Atlantic. The agenda included presentations and discussions on the future of transatlantic cooperation, with prominent participation from Member of the European Parliament Paulo Nascimento Cabral , alongside representatives from Africa, South America, the European Commission, and the CSA AANCHOR project .
All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance 2025	25-26 Sep 2025 Brussels, Belgium	In-person	AtlantECO presented policy-related outcomes, including lessons on equity, diversity, and inclusion in transatlantic research cooperation. Engagement focused on supporting North–South collaboration and shared policy dialogue.

4 AtlantECO's set of Policy briefs

4.1 Policy brief #1 - Advancing Equitable Research Cooperation in Ocean Sciences Across the Atlantic Ocean

Authors: André Abreu and Adèle Javal (Fondation Tara Océan (FTO)), Ricardo Oliveira, Diana Sousa, and Raquel Silva (Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI)), Hugo Sarmiento (Universidade Federal de São Carlos (UFSCar)), Natasha Karenzi (University of Cape Town (UCT)), Stéphane Pesant (European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL-EBI)) and Daniele Ludicone (Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SZN))

4.1.1 Executive Summary

This policy brief explores the challenges and opportunities for fostering equitable, long-term international scientific cooperation in ocean sciences across the Atlantic. Developed through collaboration between European, Brazilian, and South African partners working in the EU-funded AtlantECO project, this policy brief highlights the need for fair, ethical, and inclusive research practices that respect different cultures and local realities.

Despite various international agreements, significant barriers remain, including disparities in research capacity, funding, and technology access. Bureaucratic hurdles and the prevalence of “parachute science” further limit meaningful collaboration. Strengthening infrastructure, streamlining administrative processes, promoting research mobility, expanding open-access research, and fostering co-funding mechanisms are essential steps toward a more balanced research landscape. This brief advocates for a more inclusive and effective approach to ocean science by addressing these challenges, ensuring equitable participation in marine research and supporting sustainable ocean management.

4.1.2 Background & Context

Through its unique ecosystems and physicochemical processes, the Ocean regulates climate, cycles nutrients, produces half of Earth’s oxygen, and supports global food security. Managing the ocean sustainably is crucial to safeguarding the well-being of both human societies and the broader natural world. Advancing our scientific understanding of oceanic processes is essential for strengthening sustainable ocean governance through the development of science-based policy tools, making support for ocean research a crucial priority. Ocean

sciences encompass various research fields, from biological, chemical, geological, and physical research, to social science research studying socioecosystems (1).

Recent advancements in research tools and methods have opened up new frontiers in Ocean sciences. The significant rise in ocean data acquisition and observation – spanning environmental data, imaging data, and various -omics fields such as metagenomics, transcriptomics, and metabolomics – has opened new opportunities to enhance our understanding of ocean systems and predict their future changes. Over the past decade, new tools and methods in Ocean sciences have

- Deepened our understanding of the community structures and functions of the Ocean microbiomes (2)
- Improved Ocean circulation models (3)

To fully and equitably harness these emerging research opportunities, research collaborations in Ocean sciences must be strengthened to collectively advance our global knowledge of the Ocean.

4.1.3 Introduction

The AtlantECO project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 programme, is a research and innovation project aimed at advancing the understanding of the Atlantic Ocean to improve its management and improving predictions of future changes. Its research agenda was divided into three main scientific pillars:

- The Ocean microbiomes
- Plastics and the plastisphere
- Seascape and connectivity

AtlantECO was the first research project to be fully co-developed by the EU, Brazil and South Africa, providing equal opportunities and funding to all three partners. This project gathered 36 research partners from 13 countries, along with many collaborators across the Atlantic basin.

By equitably involving researchers from both the Northern and Southern Hemispheres, the AtlantECO project creates favourable conditions to overcome “parachute science”, a practice whereby researchers from higher-income countries collect field data in other countries without collaborating with local researchers (4-6).

These research practices driven by external expertise and priorities have been a growing concern across many scientific fields (4), including Ocean sciences (6, 7). Given its high costs and limited accessibility compared to other scientific fields, Ocean sciences strongly highlight research disparities and parachute science practices. Despite the Southern Hemisphere covering more of the Earth’s Ocean surface, Ocean Science is predominantly led by countries in the Northern Hemisphere. A UNESCO report (8) revealed that Northern countries – including the United States, Canada, and several European countries – lead global Ocean sciences in both academic publications and citations (Figure 1). Conversely, researchers from some Southern countries remain significantly underrepresented in research agendas, international conferences, and publications (6).

Figure 1 - The current research gap in Ocean science publications and citations, reproduced from UNESCO (2017)

By creating conditions for equitable research cooperation, the AtlantECO project could be perceived as a successful example of “Science Diplomacy”. This fluid concept, used to describe the interplay between science and international relations, can be divided into three categories – “Science for Diplomacy”, “Science in Diplomacy”, and “Diplomacy for Science” (9, 10). As the AtlantECO project was initiated under the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA) signed by several countries in the Northern and Southern Hemispheres, it particularly exemplifies “Diplomacy for Science” by showcasing how diplomatic efforts can facilitate and strengthen international scientific collaboration.

Current international frameworks supporting cooperation in Ocean sciences

International legally binding frameworks fostering collaborative and equitable research practices

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea and the BBNJ Treaty

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) indicates, in its 242nd article, that States and competent international organisations shall promote international cooperation in marine scientific research (11). In addition, UNCLOS provides a framework encouraging equitable access to marine research data – it promotes, in its 244th article, the flow of scientific data and information transfer from marine research, especially towards developing States, and indicates, in its 249th article, that organisations undertaking research in exclusive economic zones shall “provide access for the coastal State, at its request, to all data and samples derived from the marine scientific research project” and “provide assistance in their assessment or interpretation” (*idem*).

The new **United Nations Agreement on Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) treaty**, designed to regulate and protect biodiversity beyond national jurisdictions, was adopted in September 2024 as the third implementing agreement to the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea. Confirming the status of the High Seas as international waters with a common responsibility, the BBNJ treaty forces states to think beyond borders, and can be a major step towards an internationally designed framework for Ocean sciences cooperation. The BBNJ’s 14TH article indicates that non-monetary benefits arising from activities concerning marine genetic resources in areas beyond national jurisdiction should be shared through access to samples

and sample collections, to digital sequence information, to open scientific data, as well as encouraging research capacity-building, increased technical and scientific cooperation, and transfer of marine technology (12). The BBNJ's fifth part provides guidelines to develop Parties' marine research capacities, in particular developing States, including through technology transfers (*idem*).

The Convention on Biological Diversity and the Nagoya Protocol

The **Convention on Biological Diversity** (CBD) encourages scientific cooperation in environmental and biological sciences. For instance, its 18th article states that “contracting Parties shall promote international technical and scientific cooperation in the field of conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity”, with a special focus on building national capacities (13).

Additionally, the Nagoya Protocol, which implements the CBD, establishes a benefit-sharing mechanism between countries providing genetic resources along their coastlines, often countries in the Southern Hemisphere, and the users of these resources, including researchers. It additionally promotes research cooperation and equitable practices in marine genomics. Its 23rd article requires all Parties to “collaborate and cooperate in technical and scientific research and development programmes”, as well as to “promote and encourage access to technology by, and transfer of technology to, developing country Parties”, and that “where possible and appropriate such collaborative activities shall take place in and with a Party or the Parties providing genetic resources” (14). Its 22nd article also promotes the strengthening of countries’ “endogenous research capabilities” to add value to their genetic resources.

Other International and European frameworks supporting Ocean science cooperation

Atlantic framework

Some existing North-North, South-South, and North-South agreements – aimed at strengthening and developing transatlantic marine research collaborations – led to the All-Atlantic call for projects, from which stemmed the AtlantECO project. Building upon EU-US and EU-Canada Science & Technology agreements (15), the Galway Statement was signed by Europe, Canada, and the United States in 2013 to promote research collaborations in Ocean sciences to improve our understanding of the Atlantic Ocean. The Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance (AORA), was later established in 2015 to implement the Galway Statement, with cooperation areas including aquaculture, Ocean health and stressors, as well as seabed mapping (16).

In 2017, building on the establishment of the South–South Framework for Scientific and Technical Cooperation in oceanic research between South Africa and Brazil (15), the All-Atlantic Belém Statement was signed by the European Union, Brazil, and South Africa to deepen scientific cooperation by promoting joint research projects, capacity building, and data sharing (17).

Finally, in 2022, the All-Atlantic Ocean Research & Innovation Alliance (AAORIA) (18) declaration was signed in Washington. The signatories included the EU, Argentina, Brazil, Canada, Cabo Verde, Morocco, South Africa, and the US. This declaration builds on and reinforces the implementation of previous agreements, including the Galway and Belém statements. It also strengthens existing cooperation frameworks, such as the 2020 Administrative Arrangement on Marine Research & Innovation Cooperation between the European Commission and Morocco. Additionally, it builds on the Mindelo Arrangement between the European Commission and Cabo Verde and the EU-Argentina Administrative Arrangement, both signed in 2018 (19).

European frameworks

At the European level, two key frameworks promote research collaboration in Ocean sciences: the EU Mission “**Restore our Ocean and Waters**” and the **EU Ocean Pact**. The **EU Mission**, which supports the EU’s Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, aims to protect Ocean health. It fosters research innovation projects and cooperation among member states across major sea basins, including the Atlantic-Arctic, the Mediterranean,

the Baltic-North Sea, and the Danube-Black Sea (20). Additionally, the **EU Ocean Pact** aims to establish sustainable Ocean governance through a holistic approach encompassing a wide range of policies, from conservation and economic policies to marine research and innovation policies. As the Ocean Pact has recently been established, its potential contributions to Ocean science cooperation have yet to be assessed.

International frameworks

Finally, at the international level, the **United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development 2021-2030** (Ocean Decade), aims to strengthen Ocean sciences and support knowledge generation to protect the Ocean and support sustainable development. To implement the Ocean Decade, UNESCO's Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) was mandated to coordinate Ocean sciences, develop capacities, and promote collaborative international research projects. The IOC has been supporting capacity building and networks of scientists since the early 2000s (21). Having coordinated Ocean sciences for several decades, the IOC must now adapt to the growing diversity and complexity of Oceanic research.

4.1.4 Challenges

An effective South-North cooperation: main challenges identified

1. Uneven research capacities: networks, equipment, funding, and access to publishing

Due to the limited number of agreements supporting South-South research collaborations and the lack of funding for Southern-led initiatives, Ocean research networks in many Southern Hemisphere countries remain scarce.

Important steps in building research partnerships, such as hosting international workshops and transferring funds across borders, are less accessible in Southern countries. As explained by Asase et al. (2022) (22), biodiversity researchers from these countries often lack the funds to visit other laboratories and attend conferences to strengthen their research networks. Consequently, the lack of research networks in Southern Hemisphere countries greatly hinders regional research capacities and advancements. For instance, due to the lack of Southern research networks, the few existing research vessels remain inefficiently used.

2. Lack of co-funding

Moreover, **many countries in the Southern Hemisphere lack research infrastructure and equipment**, hindering their capacity to both **collect samples** and conduct **data analysis**. Additionally, these countries may lack the necessary equipment to meet the state-of-the-art research standards in sampling practices.

Upon data sampling and analysis, publishing in high-impact indexed journals can be very costly for researchers from Southern Hemisphere countries (23). Although publishing in some regional journals can be financially accessible, as they may require lower publishing charges, highly-cited international journals' publishing costs remain high and can be equal to Southern researchers' monthly salary (*idem*). Open Access publishing, which aims to ensure equitable access to research articles, requires researchers to pay for Article Processing Charges (APCs), thereby shifting publication costs from institutions to individual researchers (24). High-impact publications' APCs can range from 2,000 US\$ to 12,000 US\$ (*idem*).

Finally, **collaborative research projects remain rarely co-funded** by countries in the Southern Hemisphere, limiting the development of cooperative cross-border research projects driven by joint investments and perpetuating the dependency on Northern funding mechanisms and research agendas. The AtlantECO project was, for instance, solely funded by the European Union through the Horizon 2020 programme. Efforts to secure co-funding from Southern funding agencies were often hindered by a lack of understanding of the co-funding principle among decision-making boards.

Overall, these remaining gaps in research funding, networks, and equipment can lead to a brain drain from some Southern countries towards Northern countries. For example, during the AtlantECO project, after the Tara Oceans project (2009-2013), among the six South American postdocs who received funding to conduct research in European labs to explore the vast Tara Oceans dataset, most of them never returned to their home country.

3. Bureaucratic hurdles

Obtaining permits to collect samples in countries' exclusive economic zones (EEZ) has been, at times, very complex during the AtlantECO project. These processes were frequently marked by extensive bureaucracy, requiring the implementation of the Nagoya Protocol and involving the navy in multiple countries. Moreover, coordinating the imports of equipment and the exports of samples was challenging. We acknowledge that these legal needs and permit and compliance processes are mandatory in the frame of the Convention on Biological Diversity, but governments could be more involved in the legal process to facilitate the work of researchers, thereby minimising time loss and promoting efficiency. For future regional or international calls for projects, the European Union could work on a more structured science-to-policy interface, which is not the same thing as a CSA (Coordination and Supporting Action) project.

4.1.5 Recommendations

Key opportunities to improve Ocean science collaboration across the Atlantic

1. Improving research capacities in both directions

AtlantECO acknowledges the need to strengthen research capacities at all stages of the scientific process, from sampling to data analysis, in both Northern and Southern Hemispheres, to achieve successful North-South and South-South research cooperation. Technology transfers and increased research funding opportunities should strengthen countries' capacities to collect samples. It is equally important to continue increasing Southern countries' data processing and analysis capacities to guarantee equitable opportunities for data analysis. Additionally, sampling, processing, and data analysis procedures should be designed to align with locally available equipment and technologies, helping to bridge research gaps between Northern and Southern countries. In AtlantECO, researchers sometimes adapted processing standards to accommodate equipment available in certain Southern countries. This ensured that DNA processing could be carried out in lower-resourced regions without relying solely on expensive facilities. Some protocol steps were modified to match locally available resources, and sequencing platforms accessible in Southern countries were used, even if they were not the latest models.

Additionally, enhancing regional research networks would strengthen Southern countries' capacities in both sampling and data analysis. Finally, simplifying the sampling permit process and reducing administrative barriers would facilitate cross-border research efforts.

After data sampling and analysis, research findings should be shared in open databases, ensuring equitable access to both data and publishing opportunities. Open-access databases are key to fostering research cooperation, as they guarantee equal access to current research advancements and provide equal opportunities for data analysis. Several open databases facilitate data sharing, such as the European Nucleotide de Archive (ENA) and the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) for genetic data, Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science (PANGAEA) for environmental data, and EuroBio imaging and Bio studies for imaging data. Since different types of data are currently stored in separate databases, efforts should focus on creating holistic databases that integrate diverse marine data, including genetic, imaging, and environmental information. Moreover, annotated open data platforms, which integrate modelling and visualisation interfaces, should be prioritized and further developed to simplify and

catalyse data mining and analysis. To facilitate researchers' use of these databases, training programs should be provided and scientific information should be available in multiple languages.

Northern and Southern researchers should be given equal opportunities to publish in academic journals. To achieve this objective, a portion of the collaborative research projects' funding should cover publication costs. High-impact journals, such as Nature or Science, should also consider providing a waiver of publication fees or

Article Processing Charges (APCs), to account for the disparities in researchers' incomes across Northern and Southern Hemisphere countries. As long as researchers do not have equal access to publish in high-impact journals, the number of publications in these journals should not be the sole measure of a researcher's success (23).

Finally, it is important to strengthen researchers' skills and knowledge across borders. To encourage knowledge exchange and training, "brain circulation" should be encouraged, instead of "brain drain", by providing opportunities for short stays abroad (25). Additionally, young researchers across countries should be given opportunities to strengthen their research experience. The AtlantECO project illustrates how a collaborative research project can successfully involve Early-Stage Researchers (ESRs). Finally, to foster meaningful future research collaborations and knowledge exchange, scientists from the Northern Hemisphere should be encouraged to follow short training programs emphasising the importance and benefits of partnering with local researchers. These researchers shall understand that, as explained by De Vos & Schwartz (2022) (4), capacity development occurs in both directions as local researchers' expertise can largely enrich research agendas.

2. Fostering meaningful collaborative research programs

To establish successful and long-lasting collaborative research programs, it is crucial to increase funding and institutional support. This will help strengthen **regional research networks, both between the Global North and South (North-South) and among countries in the Global South (South-South)**.

Additionally, co-funding mechanisms between the Northern Hemisphere and Southern Hemisphere should be encouraged, to reduce the dependency on Northern funds as a unique source of funding. In addition to government funding sources, collaborative research projects across the Atlantic could be funded by multilateral funds. Some international environmental funds, such as the Global Environment Facility (GEF), have been criticized for power imbalances between donors and recipients, leading to distrust among some Southern Hemisphere countries (26).

It is essential to ensure that multilateral funding mechanisms for Ocean science research are fairly negotiated and governed. This would guarantee equal decision-making power and opportunities for countries across both the Southern and Northern Hemispheres.

To ensure meaningful collaborations, **local researchers should be included at all stages of the research project, including in the research design**. Involving local scientific expertise from the very beginning of a research project ensures that local needs are properly addressed and that the benefits of the research are equitably shared.

Furthermore, this reduces the dependency on external expertise and may guarantee the research project's alignment with local capacities. A notable example is the Tara Schooner Mission Microbiomes, conducted within the scope of AtlantECO, where local researchers were successfully integrated into the research agendas.

Before the Tara research schooner arrived in various regions, local and foreign researchers worked together to synthesize existing knowledge, identify research gaps, and define key research questions. During the schooner's research cruise in Brazil and South Africa, local researchers played an active role in developing

regional research projects and designing sampling strategies. After data collection during the AtlantECO Mission Microbiomes, researchers continued collaborating with local partners to align research efforts with local priorities.

Recognising and strengthening cross-cultural and cross-institutional collaboration is essential for the success of research programs. Considering cultural differences and country-specific contexts at every stage helps create an inclusive and effective research environment. Successfully navigating this cross-cultural landscape also requires valuing and integrating local knowledge, including traditional and practice-based knowledge.

Additionally, research programs should account for local institutional requirements, governance structures, and power dynamics. To support this, local collaborators can play a key role in interpreting and navigating their country's institutional context, from project design to publication of results.

4.1.6 Conclusion

To prevent parachute science and ensure equitable access to new research opportunities in Ocean Sciences ultimately achieving the science we need for the Ocean we want—stronger collaboration between the Northern and Southern Hemispheres is essential. The AtlantECO project, which fosters research cooperation between scientists from both Hemispheres, highlights both the challenges and opportunities for building fair and sustainable partnerships in Ocean sciences. Although legal frameworks support South-South and North-South collaboration in Ocean science, significant challenges remain. These include difficulties in obtaining sampling permits and disparities in research capacity between the Southern and Northern Hemispheres—particularly in infrastructure, equipment, research networks, funding, and access to publishing. To bridge these gaps, efforts to strengthen research capacities must continue.

Technology transfers and increased funding would enhance sampling and data analysis capacities, while streamlining sampling permits would facilitate research efforts. Additionally, research data should be shared through comprehensive, well-annotated open databases, and all researchers should have fair access to publishing.

Building research skills and fostering collaboration across borders is also essential. This can be achieved by offering short-term research stays, involving young researchers in projects, and training Northern researchers on the value of partnering with local experts.

Beyond capacity-building, establishing long-term, meaningful collaboration requires strengthening North-South and South-South research networks, co-funding research initiatives, reinforcing cross-cultural and cross-institutional cooperation, and ensuring local researchers are involved at every stage of a project. This approach ensures alignment with local capacities and priorities.

Finally, since advancements in Ocean science contribute to sustainable ocean governance, it is crucial to provide researchers from both Hemispheres with equal opportunities to engage in governance processes and share their expertise with policymakers.

4.1.7 References

1. Potter, R. W. K., & Pearson, B. C. (2023). *Assessing the global ocean science community: Understanding international collaboration, concerns and the current state of ocean basin research*. *Npj Ocean Sustainability*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44183-023-00020-y>
2. Zhang, H. and Ning, K. (2015). *The Tara Oceans Project: New Opportunities and Greater Challenges Ahead*. *Genomics, Proteomics & Bioinformatics*, 13(5), 275–277. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s44183-023-00020-y>

3. Fox-Kemper, B., Adcroft, A., Böning, C. W., Chassignet, E. P., Curchitser, E., Danabasoglu, G., Eden, C., England, M. H., Gerdes, R., Greatbatch, R. J., Griffies, S. M., Hallberg, R. W., Hanert, E., Heimbach, P., Hewitt, H. T., Hill, C. N., Komuro, Y., Legg, S., Le Sommer, J., ... Yeager, S. G. (2019). Challenges and Prospects in Ocean Circulation Models. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00065>
4. De Vos, A., & Schwartz, M. W. (2022). Confronting parachute science in conservation. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 4(5). <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.12681>
5. Odeny, B., & Bosurgi, R. (2022). Time to end parachute science. *PLOS Medicine*, 19(9). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1004099>
6. Stefanoudis, P. U., Licuanan, W. Y., Morrison, T. H., Talma, S., Veitayaki, J., & Woodall, L. C. (2021). Turning the tide of parachute science. *Current Biology*, 31(4), 184–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2021.01.029>
7. De Vos, A., & Schwartz, M. W. (2022). Confronting parachute science in conservation. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 4(5). <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.12681>
8. UNESCO (2017). *Global Ocean Science Report*.
9. Polejack, A. (2021). The Importance of Ocean Science Diplomacy for Ocean Affairs, Global Sustainability, and the UN Decade of Ocean Science. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.664066>
10. The Royal Society (2010). *New frontiers in Science Diplomacy*.
11. United Nations (1982). *United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea*.
12. United Nations (2023). *Agreement under the United Nations Convention on the law of the sea on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity of areas beyond national jurisdiction*.
13. Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity. (2011). *Convention on Biological Diversity*.
14. Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity. (2011). *Nagoya Protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization to the convention on biological diversity*.
15. Polejack, A., Gruber, S., & Wisz, M. S. (2021). Atlantic Ocean science diplomacy in action: The pole-to-pole All Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 8(1).
16. AORA (n.d.). AORA - Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance. Available at: <https://www.atlanticresource.org/aora/site-area/aora-cooperation-areas/aora-cooperation-areas/> (Accessed: 29 January 2025).
17. Belém statement on Atlantic Research and Innovation Cooperation. (2017). https://www.aircentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/belem_statement_2017_en.pdf
18. AAORIA (2022). All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance Declaration. The “ALL-ATLANTIC DECLARATION.” Available at: https://allatlanticocean.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/20221307_All-Atlantic-Declaration-signed.pdf (Accessed: 29 January 2025)
19. AAORIA (2024) Major Steps in Building the All-Atlantic Research Community. <https://allatlanticocean.org/who-we-are/> (Accessed: 27 January 2025).
20. European Commission (n.d.). EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters. Available at: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en#what-is-the-mission (Accessed: 29 January 2025)
21. IOC. (2005). *IOC Principles and Strategy for Capacity Building*.
22. Asase, A., Mzumara-Gawa, T. I., Owino, J. O., Peterson, A. T., & Saupe, E. (2022). Replacing “parachute science” with “global science” in ecology and conservation biology. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 4(5). <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.517>
23. Gupta, A., Reddy, B. U., & Solanki Kumar, H. (2018). Cost in high impact journals: The problem for researchers from low and middle income countries. *Public Health Review: International Journal of Public Health Research*, 5(1), 45–49. <https://doi.org/10.17511/ijphr.2018.i1.06>
24. Limaye, A. (2022). Article Processing Charges may not be sustainable for academic researchers. *MIT Science Policy Review*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.38105/spr.stucknibc5>

25. Mwampamba, T. H., Egoh, B. N., Borokini, I., & Njabo, K. (2022). Challenges encountered when doing research back home: Perspectives from African conservation scientists in the diaspora. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 4(5). <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.564>
26. Gupta, J. (2006). The Global Environment Facility in its North–South context. In *Contemporary Environmental Politics* (pp. 251–273).

4.2 Policy brief #2 - The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource: Shared capacity and equitable access for the benefit of One Ocean, One Health.

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant. This output reflects only the author’s view and the European Union or the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

4.2.1 Executive Summary

This policy brief highlights the strategic importance of the Ocean microbiome genetic resource within the interconnected frameworks of One Ocean and One Health, recognising that ocean ecosystem health, climate regulation, biodiversity, and human wellbeing are deeply interdependent. Marine microorganisms underpin global biogeochemical cycles, support marine food webs and fisheries, and provide vast genetic diversity with major potential for innovation in biotechnology, healthcare, environmental remediation, aquaculture, and climate mitigation. As such, the Ocean microbiome represents both a critical scientific frontier and a major socio-economic opportunity.

The brief emphasises that Digital Sequence Information (DSI) derived from marine genetic resources circulates globally, creating governance challenges for existing Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) frameworks under the CBD and the emerging BBNJ Agreement. Because the ocean spans Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) and Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), and because DSI can move independently of physical samples, ensuring transparency, traceability, and equitable benefit-sharing is complex. Jurisdictional fragmentation, incomplete metadata standards, and limited interoperability across databases further complicate monitoring and reporting.

Analysis of international sequence databases reveals significant geographic imbalances: the majority of Ocean microbiome samples originate from the Northern Hemisphere and from EEZs, while access to these resources is overwhelmingly dominated by countries in the Global North. These disparities highlight capacity gaps between regions and reinforce concerns about equity in the digital age.

The brief calls for strengthened monitoring and reporting protocols for DSI, including mandatory and harmonised metadata standards, coordinated integration of access metrics across major data platforms, and improved interoperability among diverse data repositories. It further supports governance approaches that balance open science with fair and equitable benefit-sharing, alongside targeted capacity-building to ensure broader global participation. By aligning science, policy, and equity, the Ocean microbiome genetic resource can be governed in a way that advances sustainable development, strengthens the blue economy, and delivers on the principles of One Ocean, One Health.

4.2.2 One Ocean, One Health

The One Ocean concept recognises that the world's Ocean is a single, interconnected system that transcends national boundaries and links ecosystems, climates, and human societies. It emphasises that activities in one region – such as plastic pollution, overfishing, or carbon emission – can have far-reaching impacts across the entire Ocean. By promoting integrated, cooperative governance and sustainable use of marine resources, the One Ocean approach encourages countries to work together to protect biodiversity and maintain ecosystem services for present and future generations. The One Ocean concept is characterised by the highly dynamic nature of the seascape compared to landscape. The seascape is shaped by physical processes such as large river plumes, circular and horizontal currents that cross the globe, as well as vertical currents driven by coastal winds and water density. This highly dynamic system is home to the Ocean microbiome, microscopic organisms such as viruses, bacteria, archaea, phytoplankton and zooplankton that drift with currents. As a result, the Ocean microbiome is highly connected across the globe.

The One Health concept recognises that the health of humans, other lifeforms, and ecosystems are closely linked and interdependent. It emphasises that many global challenges – such as emerging infectious diseases, antimicrobial resistance, food safety, and environmental degradation – cannot be effectively addressed in isolation. By encouraging collaboration across disciplines, One Health promotes innovative and coordinated solutions. Decades of research on the human microbiome – microorganisms associated with specific organs – has led to a better understanding of an individual's health as a whole, and to the detection and mitigation of specific diseases. Following the same holistic approach, there is growing evidence that the Ocean microbiome can be used to diagnose marine ecosystem health and assess capacity to support ecosystem services. The development of anti-microbial resistance by microorganisms in coastal waters is one example of the close connection between the Ocean microbiome and human health. Decades of research on plankton have revealed the importance of the Ocean microbiome in regulating the Earth's climate and responding to anthropogenic carbon emissions, and in supporting marine food webs and fisheries.

Figure 1. One Ocean, One Health. LEFT: The human microbiome is diagnostic of human health. MIDDLE: The Ocean microbiome is diagnostic of Ocean health. RIGHT: The One Ocean concept relies on the highly dynamic nature of the seascape compared to landscape, leading to high connectivity of the Ocean microbiome.

Scientific Importance

Fundamental research on the Ocean microbiome is essential to better understand:

- **The fabric of marine ecosystems:** The ocean microbiome underpins marine food webs by driving primary production (e.g., photosynthetic microbes) and nutrient recycling, forming the biological base that supports all higher marine life.
- **Evolution and biodiversity:** The ocean microbiome represents one of the largest reservoirs of genetic diversity on the planet. Studying its genes reveals evolutionary innovations, novel metabolic pathways, and previously unknown branches of the tree of life.
- **Global biogeochemical cycles:** Marine microorganisms regulate major Earth systems by mediating the cycling of carbon, nitrogen, sulfur, and phosphorus. Their genetic pathways control processes such as carbon sequestration and nitrogen fixation, which are central to climate regulation.
- **Ecosystem stressors and drivers of change:** Microbial community structure and gene expression respond rapidly to environmental change, making the ocean microbiome a sensitive indicator of ocean warming, acidification, and deoxygenation, while also influencing climate feedback mechanisms.
- **Discovering underexplored environments:** Metagenomic research on marine microbes uncovers new enzymes, biochemical processes, and survival strategies (e.g., adaptation to extreme pressure, temperature, and salinity), expanding fundamental scientific understanding of life under extreme and variable conditions.

Socio-Economic potential

The Ocean microbiome genetic resources hold significant potential for economic development and innovation across multiple sectors:

- **Biodiscovery and healthcare:** The ocean microbiome contains vast, untapped genetic material that lead to the development of medicines, including cancer treatments, antibiotics, and anti-inflammatory drugs.
- **Environmental remediation:** Microorganisms from the ocean microbiome are used in bioremediation to clean up oil spills, heavy metals, and other pollutants. This capability supports industries focused on environmental cleanup, reducing costs and enhancing sustainability efforts.
- **Aquaculture Innovation:** Combined with aquaculture feed, microbial strains from the marine environment help promote growth, boost fish immunity and reduce disease outbreaks, leading to lower treatment costs and higher productivity.
- **Industrial applications:** The enzymes and proteins derived from ocean microorganisms are used in various industries, such as waste processing, biofuels production, and plastics degradation, offering more efficient and sustainable production methods while driving economic growth.
- **Climate change mitigation:** Ocean microbes play a crucial role in carbon cycling and the regulation of greenhouse gases. By harnessing these microbes, we can develop technologies for carbon sequestration, helping mitigate climate change impacts while creating new economic opportunities in green technologies.

Policy Impacts

Investment in research and innovation related to the Ocean microbiome helps:

- **Achieve healthy and productive oceans (UNSDG14)** through better and more accurate monitoring and management of marine ecosystems.
- **Avoid significant adverse impacts**, including those of climate change through better assessments and forecasts of marine ecosystem vulnerabilities.
- **Develop ecosystem services** to ensure the long-term sustainable management of marine resources.
- **Increase EU leadership and competitiveness** in the blue economy by developing new technologies and new value chains.
- **Improve the professional skills and competences** needed for a rapidly changing blue economy.

The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource

Marine Genetic Resources (MGRs) refer to any biological materials of marine origin, including the functional units of heredity (DNA & RNA) as well as their expression into the structural units of life such as proteins, metabolites and whole organisms. The Ocean Microbiome genetic resource refers more specifically to MGRs from marine microorganisms, including viruses, bacteria, archaea, phytoplankton, and zooplankton. **Digital Sequence Information (DSI)** refers broadly to any data derived from genetic resources. In the case of the Ocean microbiome, DSI generally results from the sequencing, mass spectrometry and imaging of whole organisms, genes, proteins and metabolites. The Ocean microbiome genetic resource holds significant scientific, ecological, and economic value, supporting climate regulation, food webs, biotechnology, and healthcare innovation. Because the Ocean microbiome is highly interconnected across national boundaries, the governance and use of this genetic resource raise important transboundary and equity considerations.

Figure 2. The Ocean Microbiome Genetic Resource. Digital Sequence Information resulting from the sequencing, spectrometry and imaging of the Ocean microbiome genetic resource – including whole organisms, genes, proteins and metabolites – supports humanity in areas such as food security, climate regulation and healthcare.

Shared Capacity and Equitable Access

Digital Sequence Information (DSI) derived from the Ocean microbiome genetic resource may originate from samples collected in:

- **Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ)** – EEZs are maritimes zones extending up to 200 nautical miles (370 km) from a coastal state's shoreline. In this zone, the coastal state has sovereign rights over natural resources (both living and non-living) in the water column, seabed, and subsoil. This includes rights to explore, exploit, conserve, and manage marine resources, as well as jurisdiction over activities such as marine research and environmental protection.

- **Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ)** – ABNJs are parts of the Ocean that lie outside any national jurisdiction. These areas are typically located beyond the 200 nautical miles of an EEZ, and they encompass the high seas and the deep seabed (the area known as the Area, under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, UNCLOS). In ABNJs, no single nation has sovereignty, and the resources are considered to be part of the common heritage of mankind, managed under international frameworks. Key governance mechanisms in ABNJs include treaties such as the BBNJ Agreement and the United Nations.

Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) was developed under the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol. It set the foundation for shared capacity, equity and international coordination. Since then, the definition of DSI and the establishment of the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) agreement have posed some challenges:

- **DSI challenges the ABS paradigm:** ABS was designed around the management of physical access to tangible genetic material. DSI bypasses these control points because users may utilise sequence data without conventional access-agreements, thus creating gaps in governance.
- **Gaps between international frameworks:** Both the CBD and the BBNJ Agreement now recognise DSI, yet institutional mechanisms, monitoring tools, and legal clarity are still evolving and incomplete.
- **Jurisdictional fragmentation:** Differences between EEZs (national jurisdiction) and ABNJ (shared governance) complicate regulation, traceability, and equitable benefit-sharing.
- **Lack of transparency and traceability:** Mandatory metadata standards, interoperable clearing-houses, and reporting protocols are critically needed to track DSI provenance and usage.

A number of governance mechanisms and policy approaches are under discussion to address these challenges. Each has its own set of advantages and drawbacks, reflecting the complexities of managing data, ensuring fair benefit-sharing, and balancing open science with equity.

- **Multilateral fund for DSI benefit-sharing** encourages global collaboration and preserves open access to scientific data. It simplifies the implementation of benefit-sharing by pooling resources from various stakeholders. On the other hand, weak traceability of where and how DSI is used can complicate monitoring and enforcing benefit-sharing. It is also complex to implement effectively at a large scale.
- **Jurisdictional Differentiation (EEZ vs ABNJ)** recognises and respects national sovereignty over marine resources within Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) while maintaining international cooperation for Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ). On the other hand, this dual system (different governance for EEZs and ABNJs) can create administrative challenges and increase the complexity of governance across different regions.
- **Database integration and metadata tagging** helps improve the transparency of DSI use by linking data to its original source, making it easier to track the flow of genetic resources and ensure that benefits are shared fairly. On the other hand, the tagging DSI can slow down the process of data sharing and introduce technical costs, which could make database integration more difficult to manage.
- **Capacity-building and non-monetary benefit-sharing** promotes equity and participation, particularly in developing coastal states, by providing resources and support to build local research capacity and technological infrastructure. On the other hand, this approach lacks direct financial returns, which may make it less appealing for some stakeholders focused on immediate economic benefits.

The Geopolitical Context

The Earth's surface can be divided between sovereign nations on land, Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) in coastal waters, and Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJs) in the high seas. Together the EEZs and ABNJs cover 71% of the surface of the globe, and – with an average depth of 3,700 metres – provide over a billion cubic kilometers of habitat for the Ocean microbiome. This genetic resource represents a huge potential for

scientific, innovation and economic growth. Marine Genetic Resources (MGRs) collected within EEZs fall under national sovereignty, while those collected within ABNJs are governed by international frameworks. Once converted into Digital Sequence Information (DSI), however, data originating from MGRs can circulate globally without clear jurisdictional anchors, complicating distinctions between sovereign rights and shared governance. The geographic distribution of the Ocean microbiome genetic resource between EEZs and ABNJs and between the Northern and Southern Hemispheres is therefore relevant when discussing shared capacity and equitable access to that resource. The high seas (ABNJs) cover approximately 50% of the planet's surface compared to only 21% for EEZs. This contrast is more pronounced in the Southern Hemisphere with a greater proportion of high seas (66%) compared to EEZs (12%), whereas it is less pronounced in the Northern Hemisphere with similar proportions of EEZs (28%) and high seas (38%).

The One Ocean, One Health concept fundamentally cuts across the geographic divisions or boundaries of sovereign nations on land, Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) and Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJs). However, differences in the scientific, economic and political interests of sovereign nations, combined with contrasting capacity to exploit the Ocean microbiome genetic resource, challenge the One Ocean, One Health concept. The governance mechanisms outlined in the previous above aim to balance the One Ocean, One Health approach with national interests, ensuring that both scientific advancement and equitable distribution of benefits are considered.

Geographic coverage

Figure 3. Geographic coverage of Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ), Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) and Land masses. It is important to note that joint regimes (e.g. waters bordering Antarctica) and overlapping claims are included in the statistics shown here for the EEZs. **LEFT:** The Southern Hemisphere is dominated by the ABNJ (66%) compared to the Northern Hemisphere where the ABNJ, EEZs and Land masses cover nearly equal shares. **CENTRE:** Globally, the ABNJ covers half (50%) of the planet. **RIGHT:** Global map showing the distribution of ABNJ, EEZs and Land masses in the Southern and Northern Hemispheres.

Monitoring and Reporting protocols regarding Digital Sequence Information (DSI)

Monitoring and Reporting protocols are essential to track the provenance, use and flow of DSI derived from the Ocean microbiome genetic resources and other biological resources. These protocols aim to ensure transparency, accountability, and compliance with international frameworks like the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol. They require that standard metadata, such as the origin and context of samples, are embedded in digital data repositories. By implementing consistent tracking systems, these protocols help monitor the utilization of DSI, ensuring that benefits are shared equitably with resource-providing countries, while also safeguarding the integrity of open science. Although progress is being

made in developing and implementing Monitoring and Reporting protocols for DSI, significant work remains to harmonize global standards, enhance transparency, and ensure equitable benefit-sharing in the digital age.

With the aim to highlight challenges around monitoring and reporting on DSI, we attempted to provide metrics about the provenance and access to Ocean microbiome genetic resources. Statistics were obtained from the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), one of the three sequence data archives of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC) where scientists deposit and access DSI as well as metadata of the associated genetic resources. The three data archives (ENA in Europe, GenBank in the USA, and DDBJ in Japan) mirror their data and metadata, so that **provenance statistics** obtained from one of the three archives reflect the entire INSDC database. On the other hand, **accession statistics** obtained from one of the three archives reflect only the accesses made through that archive. The number of accessions presented here therefore underestimates the total number of accesses from the INSDC by perhaps two-thirds, and the statistics regarding the origin of accessed records or the origin of users accessing records reflect only the user community of the European Nucleotides Archive, which may differ from that of GenBank in the USA, and DDBJ in Japan. Additionally, only access to sample metadata is considered here rather than access to the DSI themselves (sequences and their annotations), which is ultimately a more meaningful metric and would likely be some orders of magnitude greater than the number of accesses shown here.

As of January 2025, the INSDC counted over 46 million sample records, 2 million of which were identified as Marine Genetic Resources (MGRs). Our analysis of available provenance metadata – including geolocation, sampling depth, taxonomy and sequencing strategy – indicated that a quarter of those samples (0.5 million) targeted the Ocean microbiome genetic resource, but only 0.3 million had geolocation. At that date, these records were accessed nearly 0.8 million times via ENA metadata queries alone.

Provenance of Ocean microbiome genetic resources

Figure 4. Provenance of Digital Sequence Information (DSI) from Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) and Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). It is important to note that joint regimes (e.g. waters bordering Antarctica) and overlapping claims are included in the statistics shown here for the EEZs. **LEFT:** The vast majority of DSI (83%) originates from the Northern Hemisphere. In both Hemispheres, the vast majority of DSI originates from EEZs (90% in the North & 87% in the South) compared to the ABNJ. **CENTRE:** Globally, DSI originates predominantly from EEZs (90%) compared to the ABNJ. **RIGHT:** Global map showing from which Countries' EEZs the DSI originate, with greatest numbers (darker green shades) from the EEZs of the United States of America, China, Australia, Canada and Japan. (data obtained from ENA in January 2025 <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf1295>)

Overall, **access to Ocean microbiome genetic resources reflects their availability.** When comparing the two hemispheres, the vast majority of samples (83%) originate from the Northern Hemisphere (Figure 4), which is reflected in the number of accesses (82%) from the Northern Hemisphere (Figure 5). When comparing marine jurisdiction areas (EEZs and ABNJs), samples originate predominantly from EEZs (90%) compared to the ABNJ (Figure 4), which is also reflected in the number of accesses (84%) from EEZs (Figure 5). In other words, communities interested in Ocean microbiome genetic resources tend to exploit all available resources rather

than regional subsets. This may result from growing interest in addressing global questions, and greater capacity to exploit large data bases using machine learning and Earth system models.

Globally, **Ocean microbiome genetic resources are collected overwhelmingly in the Northern Hemisphere (83%), highlighting an important geographic gap.** Despite equivalent areas covered by marine waters (ABNJs + EEZs) in the Southern and Northern Hemispheres (78% vs. 66% respectively; Figure 3), less than 20% of Ocean microbiome genetic resources originate from the Southern Hemisphere (Figure 4). In both Hemispheres, **Ocean microbiome genetic resources are collected overwhelmingly in EEZs (87-90%)** rather than ABNJ, and statistics show that samples originating from EEZs were collected in greater numbers in the national waters of the United States of America, China, Australia, Canada and Japan (Figure 4). Not surprisingly, this reflects greater ease with which research is conducted in coastal EEZs, and more generally, the concentration of developed countries with high income economies in the Northern Hemisphere. From a scientific and economic point of view, there is a strong interest in filling this gap and collecting Ocean microbiome genetic resources from the underexplored ABNJs, particularly in the Southern Hemisphere. Policy agreements and diplomatic initiatives such as the [All Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance](#) contribute to fill this gap.

Access to Ocean microbiome genetic resources

Figure 5. Access to Digital Sequence Information (DSI) from Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (ABNJ) and Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs). It is important to note that joint regimes (e.g. waters bordering Antarctica) and overlapping claims are included in the statistics shown here for the EEZs. **LEFT:** The vast majority of accesses (82%) target DSI from the Northern Hemisphere. In both Hemispheres, the vast majority of accesses targeted DSI from EEZs (88% in the North & 68% in the South) compared to ABNJ. **CENTRE:** Globally, the vast majority of accesses target DSI from EEZs (84%) compared to ABNJ. **RIGHT:** Global map showing which Countries access DSI, with greatest numbers (darker green shades) by Germany, Italy, the United States of America, China and the United Kingdom. (data obtained from ENA in January 2025 <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf1295>)

Adding to the fact that Ocean microbiome genetic resources largely originate from the Northern Hemisphere, our results clearly show that **countries from the Northern Hemisphere overwhelmingly dominate (99%) the number of accesses, and the exploitation of genetic resources**, irrespectively of the latitude at which these were collected (Figure 6). This of course reinforces ongoing debates about equity, capacity, and fair benefit-sharing in the digital age. On the other hand, the fact that Ocean microbiome genetic resources are accessed in greater numbers by users located in Germany, Italy, the United States of America, China and the United Kingdom (Figure 5) may simply reflect ENA's user community, and such statistics would likely differ if access via other INSDC archives are considered.

Figure 6. Number of accesses to Digital Sequence Information (DSI) by countries from the Northern and Southern Hemispheres, broken down by latitude of origin of accessed DSI. All latitudes confounded, the vast majority of accesses (99%) are by Countries from the Northern Hemisphere (LEFT, blue) compared to accesses (1%) by Countries from the Southern Hemisphere (RIGHT, orange). (data obtained from ENA in January 2025 <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf1295>)

4.2.3 Recommendations

Policymakers and international organisations are considering several actions to ensure equitable, transparent, and effective governance of marine digital sequence information (DSI). These are outlined in this policy brief and we support them fully. With the aim to highlight challenges around monitoring and reporting on DSI, we attempted to provide metrics about the provenance and access to Ocean microbiome genetic resources. These are our recommendations:

- **Metadata about the origin and context of samples are often incomplete** – If monitoring and reporting protocols aim at providing metrics about the provenance of DSI, governance protocols from the CBD and BBNJ should enforce the adoption and usage of existing and perhaps more prescriptive metadata standards such as those developed by the Genomics Standards Consortium (GSC).
- **There are multiple platforms and entry points to access DSI** – If monitoring and reporting protocols aim at providing metrics about access to DSI, a coordinated approach is needed in order to harvest and integrate access metrics from multiple DSI access points, including at minimum the INSDC archives, the various genomics analysis platforms such as MGnify, and data aggregators such as OBIS and GBIF.
- **DSI generated from marine genetic resources include many data types** – Digital Sequence Information may be obtained from the sequencing, spectrometry and imaging of the Ocean microbiome genetic resource, which data are archived in various domain-specific data bases. If the aim is to provide metrics about the full breadth of DSI, policy actions are needed to support the development of data interoperability across domains.

4.2.4 References

Humphries ed. (2025) *Decoding Marine Genetic Resource Governance Under the BBNJ Agreement*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-72100-7>

Yuan David, Ahamed Alisha, Athar Awais, Devaraj Rajkumar, Gupta Dipayan, Haseeb Muhammad, Ihsan Maira, Ivanov Eugene, Kadhirvelu Vishnukumar, Khen Amnon, Kumar Manish, Lathi Ankur, Liyanage Isuru, Meszaros Lili, O’Cathail Colman, Pauperio Joana, Paz Ruben, Pesant Stephane, Rahman Nadim, Rajan Jeena, Tutis Iva, Uentouratou Marianna,

Ujijayaraja Senthilnathan, Waheed Zahra, Woollard Peter, Burdett Tony, Cochrane Guy, Sarkans Ugis (2026) **The European Nucleotide Archive in 2025**. *Nucleic Acids Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaf1295>

4.3 Policy brief #3 - Blue Economy and nature-based solutions: A sustainable future for Atlantic Industries

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4.3.1 Executive Summary

This policy brief highlights the urgent need to align scientific innovation with marine policy, enhance transatlantic cooperation across Europe, Africa, and South America, and accelerate the uptake of bio-based and nature-based solutions to support a Sustainable Blue Economy. Despite a robust framework of international and European policies, implementation remains fragmented, with limited integration of scientific knowledge into policy.

Marine microbiomes represent a promising frontier for sustainability, offering new opportunities for environmental restoration and economic growth. However, realising their potential requires coherent regulatory frameworks and equitable access and benefit-sharing mechanisms. The AtlantECO project demonstrates the power of interdisciplinary research, collaborative innovation networks, and evidence-based policy to tackle ocean challenges across the Atlantic basin.

Key recommendations in this brief focus on reinforcing transatlantic collaboration, improving the science-policy interface, and building shared systems for ocean knowledge and innovation. These measures are essential to advancing climate resilience, ocean health, and equitable economic development throughout the All-Atlantic community. The brief ultimately aims to elevate awareness, build capacity, promote responsible practices, and catalyse a Blue Growth strategy that unites the All-Atlantic region, aligned with AtlantECO's mission.

4.3.2 Background and Context

The Atlantic Ocean is at the core of the global maritime economy and a vital provider of ecosystem services. As human activity intensifies, the repercussions cascade across marine ecosystems, amplifying the impact of climate change, overexploitation, pollution, and other environmental stressors.

The AtlantECO project steps into this context by focusing on the structure and functioning of the Atlantic Ocean ecosystem, with particular emphasis on the **microbiome, plastics and the plastisphere**, and **seascape connectivity**. Recognising the lack of comprehensive knowledge about the Atlantic Ocean ecosystem's structure, functioning, health, and services, AtlantECO aims to develop and apply a novel, unifying framework for providing knowledge-based resources to support decision-making, design policies, and engage with citizens to encourage responsible behaviour to manage the Atlantic system and protect its ecosystem services provision.

Amid rapid population growth and accelerating climate change, a paramount challenge emerges: **preserving ecosystem services and good environmental status**. AtlantECO's efforts align with the **Atlantic Maritime Strategy**, which aspires to cultivate a sustainable Blue Economy in the Atlantic area, harmonising economic development with environmental preservation and climate adaptation.

Europe has introduced a range of policy incentives and frameworks to promote sustainable Blue Economy practices, particularly in alignment with the European Green Deal, the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and the EU Blue Economy strategy. These incentives include funding programmes, regulatory frameworks, and innovation support mechanisms. Depending on the funding scheme, these tools can act at European-, regional-, national-, and bilateral-levels.

The **European Ocean Pact** [1] was adopted on June 5, 2025, by the European Commission as a comprehensive strategy to address the challenges facing the ocean, including pollution, climate change, and overexploitation of marine resources. The Sustainable Blue Economy is one of the six priority areas.

The **EU Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy** [2] aims to promote sustainable growth in ocean-related economic activities while protecting the marine environment. It is a key part of the **European Green Deal**, aligning marine activities with climate and environmental goals. The strategy sets a vision for a climate-neutral, sustainable, and circular Blue Economy, focusing on decarbonising maritime transport, developing marine renewable energy, promoting circularity in sectors like fishing and ship recycling, and preserving coastal biodiversity. It encourages synergies between marine sectors and nature-based solutions (NbS).

The **EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030** [3] is a comprehensive plan to protect and restore nature across Europe, aiming to reverse biodiversity loss by 2030. Key elements include protecting at least 30% of land and sea in the EU, restoring degraded ecosystems, and addressing the drivers of biodiversity loss. The strategy also promotes restoration of marine ecosystems as essential to a resilient Blue Economy, supporting the integration of NbS into coastal zone management.

Portugal, Ireland, France, and Spain have national Blue Economy strategies or roadmaps aligned with EU goals. The **Atlantic Maritime Strategy** and related action plans [4] promote cross-border cooperation and innovation in the Atlantic basin.

Alongside strategic frameworks and regulatory developments, the European Union has mobilised substantial funding and financing mechanisms to catalyse the transition toward a Sustainable Blue Economy and accelerate marine-based innovation. The **European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF)** allocates €6.1 billion (2021-2027) to support sustainable fisheries, aquaculture, and Blue Economy innovation. Managed primarily through national programmes co-financed by the EU and Member States, EMFAF supports eco-innovation, coastal resilience, marine biodiversity restoration, and adaptation to climate change. Under its directly managed instruments, EMFAF also launched the **BlueInvest initiative**, which blends public and private capital to support early-stage Blue Economy SMEs and startups.

Horizon Europe, the EU's flagship research and innovation programme, supports sustainable ocean solutions under **Cluster 6 - "Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment"**. This includes targeted investments in biodiversity and ecosystem services, clean environment and zero pollution, and sustainable bio-based systems. Particular emphasis is placed on the development of NbS, circular economy practices, marine biotechnology, and the creation of sustainable blue value chains. Under **Cluster 5 - "Climate, Energy, and Mobility"**, Horizon Europe targets climate neutrality in the maritime sector, including offshore renewable energy, decarbonisation of maritime transport, and climate adaptation strategies for coastal and marine areas, all crucial for the Sustainable Blue Economy.

Complementing these efforts, the **EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030"** aims to protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems by integrating research and innovation with citizen engagement and blue investments. By addressing the ocean and inland waters as a single interconnected system, the Mission Ocean plays a central role in achieving the EU's climate neutrality and biodiversity goals.

Despite these advances, the ocean governance landscape remains fragmented, with overlapping jurisdictions, regulatory inconsistencies, and gaps between policy ambition and implementation. Global frameworks such as the **United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS)** and the **Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)** provide foundational legal regimes for marine governance, environmental protection, and equitable access to genetic resources. The **Nagoya Protocol (2010)** and the recently adopted **Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Agreement (2023)** address critical gaps in the sustainable use and benefit-sharing of marine genetic resources, including those relevant to microbiome research. Within the EU, instruments like the **Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)** and the **Common Fisheries Policy (CFP)** support regional marine conservation and resource management.

However, the uptake of innovative, sustainable solutions remains weak, often hindered by limited policy coherence, insufficient integration of scientific knowledge, and underdeveloped mechanisms for cross-border collaboration and benefit-sharing. The **UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030)** offers an opportunity to improve ocean knowledge, foster international collaboration, and strengthen science-policy interfaces, although it is not legally binding.

Addressing these policy and implementation gaps is essential to realizing the goals of the Sustainable Blue Economy and ensuring that innovations in areas, such as microbiome research and bio-based solutions, contribute meaningfully to ocean health and resilience.

4.3.3 Introduction

Sustainable Blue Economy refers to the sustainable use of ocean and water resources for economic growth, scientific and technological innovation, improved livelihoods, and job creation, while preserving the health of marine and freshwater ecosystems. The Blue Economy includes all activities that are marine-based or marine-related, encompassing not only traditional sectors but also emerging and innovative sectors, i.e. less mature industries linked to the marine environment, which bring new opportunities for investment and hold potential for future development of coastal communities. These include offshore renewable energy, aquaculture, seabed extractive activities, marine biotechnology and bioprospecting.

Recognising the potential to make a significant contribution to economic growth, job creation, and sustainability transition, the EU has established 12 Blue Economy sectors [5]:

1. Blue Biotechnology
2. Coastal tourism
3. Desalination of seawater
4. Infrastructure and robotics
5. Marine living resources (e.g. fisheries and aquaculture)
6. Marine non-living resources (e.g. extraction of crude petroleum or other minerals)
7. Marine renewable energy [MRE]
8. Maritime defence
9. Maritime transport
10. Port activities
11. Shipbuilding and repair
12. Research and innovation

With an annual economic value estimated at €2.3 trillion, ocean-linked sectors, or the ‘Blue Economy’ is equivalent to the world’s 7th largest economy [6]. In 2020, the export value of the ocean economy was €1.2 trillion, with exports of ocean-based goods estimated to be €619 billion, and exports of ocean-based services €571 billion. When looking at the top ocean economy exporters, the European Union is by far the biggest exporter of ocean-based goods and services, with €417 billion of exports in 2020 [7].

According to 2022 data, the established sectors of the EU Blue Economy directly employed close to 4.82 million people and generated around €890.6 billion in turnover and €250.7 billion in gross value added (GVA). Furthermore, the estimates suggest that the EU Blue Economy sectors continued to grow in 2023, contributing €263 billion to the EU GVA and employing 4.88 million persons. Between 2012 and 2022, the Blue Economy's real GVA grew by an estimated 37%, accounting for 2% of total EU GVA growth during this period [8].

Coastal tourism remains the largest blue economy sector, generating 33% of the EU Blue Economy GVA and 53% of total EU Blue Economy's employment in 2022. The EU offshore wind energy sector is one of the fastest growing sectors in the EU economy, with a 42% increase in GVA compared to 2021. This growth boosted the sector's profits, which reached €4.1 billion in 2022 [8].

The 2025 edition of the EU Blue Economy report [8] places special focus on the energy transition in EU maritime transport and the fishing fleet, as well as the potential of NbS against the impacts of climate change in EU coastal areas. NbS provides opportunities to strengthen coastal protection and reduce the risks of flooding and coastal erosion. Coastal flooding causes economic damages of € 1.2 billion per year in the EU [9]. By 2100, annual damages could reach €1 trillion, with 3.9 million people exposed to coastal flooding every year in Europe [10] [11] [12].

NbS has been gaining increasing attention as a resilient and adaptable strategy for safeguarding coastlines. Compared with traditional engineering approaches, they can be more sustainable and cost-effective, leveraging natural processes and ecosystems such as wetlands, mangroves, dunes, and reefs, to reduce the impacts of coastal flooding and erosion while simultaneously enhancing biodiversity and supporting local communities. By integrating ecological restoration with human infrastructure needs, these approaches not only provide physical protection but also contribute to carbon sequestration, water quality improvement, and recreational opportunities, making them a holistic solution for coastal resilience.

In light of the environmental repercussions of human activities, political action was taken to define a Sustainable Blue Economy, as the EU is fostering the transition to a Sustainable Blue Economy as part of the European Green Deal. This approach guarantees coherence across the Blue Economy sectors, facilitating their coexistence and synergies within the maritime space, without harming or compromising the health of the environment. The EU has been promoting the Sustainable Blue Economy as a central motor in alleviating the pressures on natural resources and fostering climate change mitigation and adaptation. In this context, the need to develop and promote Sustainable Blue Economy activities has become critical.

4.3.4 Microbiomes and Bio-based innovation

Marine microbiomes are emerging as key assets in the Blue Economy and NbS. These microscopic ecosystems - complex communities of microorganisms such as bacteria, archaea, fungi, protists and metazoans - play vital roles in nutrient cycling, climate regulation, and the health of marine species and habitats. Advances in DNA sequencing and bioinformatics are now unlocking the potential of microbiomes for bio-based innovation across sectors, including aquaculture, bioremediation, pharmaceuticals, and sustainable materials. [DS1]

Marine biological prospecting includes the discovery of novel genes and biological compounds from the ocean environment that can lead to commercial development of pharmaceuticals, enzymes, cosmetics, biodegradable plastics and other products. There is growing commercial interest in marine genetic resources, with patent applications increasing rapidly at rates exceeding 12% per year. A majority of these patents have been filed by a few highly developed countries, highlighting the increasing biotechnology capacity gap between nations [13]. Recent research reveals that marine gene sequences referenced in patent filings are quite numerous. A 2018 study reported 12,998 sequences from 862 marine species [14]. More recent analyses, however, show a sharp increase in marine genetic data associated with patent activity. The MARine

Bioprospecting PATent (MABPAT) database (2024) identifies over 92,550 protein-coding sequences linked to 4,779 patent filings, spanning more than 1,000 marine species [15]. This rapid growth reflects the expanding commercial interest in marine genetic resources and underscores the need for robust governance frameworks ensuring equitable access, benefit sharing, and responsible innovation in marine biotechnology.

For Atlantic countries, investing in marine microbiome research and infrastructure can catalyse high-value innovation, promote ecosystem resilience, and support the development of sustainable, biotechnology-driven industries. [DS2] To ensure fair access and benefit-sharing from microbiome resources, coherent regulatory frameworks and multilateral cooperation are essential, especially in transboundary marine regions.

Capacity-building and technology transfer relating to marine bioprospecting are likely to increase with the ongoing implementation of the Nagoya Protocol to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), under which researchers expecting to commercialize natural products are required to share benefits with the host country. These benefits include both monetary and non-monetary benefits; the latter generally consist of partnerships between researchers in developing and industrial countries, capacity building, and the transfer of appropriate technologies (for example, setting up laboratory facilities in low- and middle-income countries universities) [13].

Developing countries are faced with scientific capacity challenges, including a lack of expertise in taxonomy, difficulties in attracting and retaining qualified marine scientists, and limited research facilities and financial resources. Information sharing, capacity building, and the transfer of technology, including through the participation of developing states in research activities, are considered essential to address the general lack of scientific and other knowledge on marine genetic resources in these countries. Research collaborations between institutions from industrial and low- and middle-income countries have provided both training opportunities and technology transfer, although such collaborations have so far been ad hoc and somewhat limited in scope [13].

Building on these foundational needs and opportunities, the AtlantECO project exemplifies how transdisciplinary, collaborative research can drive sustainable blue bio-based innovation. The project combines oceanography, molecular biology, data science, and socioeconomics to deepen understanding and assessment of ecosystem services in the Atlantic. Using multiple platforms and technologies, including phenomics, the project fills critical knowledge and geographic gaps by integrating large-scale imaging and genetic data with environmental datasets. This supports the development of new ocean indicators and improves predictive models, contributing towards the Ocean Digital Twin [16], ultimately contributing to more informed, sustainable marine governance across the Atlantic. With a special focus on the role of microbiomes in regulating key ecosystems, AtlantECO leverages the contribution of these microscopic communities to ocean health and resilience, as well as to sustainable innovations in biotechnology, aquaculture, and environmental remediation.

AtlantECO also fosters pan-Atlantic Innovation Networks to strengthen cooperation between public and private stakeholders around shared Blue Growth goals. These networks aim to promote knowledge exchange across Europe, Africa, and South America on key socio-economic issues, supporting more sustainable and resilient ocean management strategies, including Blue Economy and NbS.

To clearly demonstrate the exploitation potential of AtlantECO knowledge towards a range of applications, five case studies have been defined within the project, two of which demonstrate the applicability of sustainable Blue Economy and NbS methods, technologies, results, and outputs for real applications.

1. The **Molecular Bioprospecting** case study focuses on the discovery of new enzymes digesting microplastics, as well as enzymes with high-value applications in diagnosis and molecular research.

Relevant industry stakeholders are directly involved in the exploitation phase as 'early adopters' of these specific project results.

2. The **Bioprospecting for organisms and impact of drilling in Brazil** case study collaborates with the industry to bioprospect microbial genes involved in hydrocarbon degradation near oil extraction sites, aiming to develop bioremediation tools. It also evaluates offshore oil drilling impacts through field studies and laboratory experiments exposing plankton to drilling materials. This work aims to inform future regulations and best practices in the gas and oil industry.

Together, these efforts illustrate how AtlantECO operationalises marine microbiome research and bio-based innovation to support a sustainable Blue Economy and resilient nature-based solutions across the Atlantic region.

4.3.5 Key recommendations

Ensuring the sustainability of the oceans is fundamental not only for maintaining marine biodiversity but also for securing the future of human endeavours that rely on the ocean's health. Realising the full benefits of a Sustainable Blue Economy will depend greatly on enhanced cooperation across the Atlantic, especially between the European Union, African and South American nations. These territories are intrinsically linked by shared marine systems, migratory patterns, climatic influences, and common economic and social interests in coastal and oceanic environments. By uniting around common sustainability objectives, they can create stronger and more inclusive frameworks that protect the marine environment while advancing prosperity and fairness.

Recommendation 1: Give precedence to the co-creation of evidence-led policies for ocean governance, facilitate the exchange of marine technologies, strengthening of local capacities, and synchronising efforts to track biodiversity and combat pollution. Cooperating through joint scientific efforts, mutual learning platforms, and standardised regulations is essential to address cross-border issues like unregulated fishing, marine ecosystem decline, pollution, and climate-driven changes to the ocean.

Recommendation 2: Reinforce the interface between scientific research and policy development to strengthen cooperation at the Atlantic scale. Integrate science more effectively into governance frameworks to ensure that decisions are grounded in the latest evidence and reflect the complexity of marine ecosystems. This requires creating more structured and inclusive pathways for dialogue between researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders across regions, facilitating mutual understanding, responsiveness to emerging knowledge, and shared responsibility for sustainable ocean stewardship.

Recommendation 3: Develop shared systems for ocean knowledge and innovation that transcend national boundaries. Establish open, interoperable data platforms, collaborative research infrastructures, and co-designed monitoring strategies to improve the way scientific insights inform marine governance. Such transatlantic knowledge hubs would not only enhance transparency and policy coherence, but also enable more equitable access to data, tools, and technologies, particularly benefiting countries with limited scientific capacity. In doing so, they would contribute to a more integrated and resilient Atlantic community, united by a common commitment to protecting ocean health and fostering sustainable development.

4.3.6 Conclusions

The health and resilience of the Atlantic Ocean are foundational to the well-being of its bordering nations and the global community. However, fragmented governance, limited integration of scientific knowledge, and weak uptake of innovative solutions continue to hinder progress toward sustainability. The AtlantECO project

has demonstrated that a transdisciplinary, cooperative, and science-informed approach can effectively overcome many of these challenges.

To unlock the full potential of a Sustainable Blue Economy, countries on both sides of the Atlantic must deepen collaboration, embrace bio-based innovation, and ensure policies are driven by up-to-date science and supported by inclusive governance frameworks. Marine microbiomes, in particular, represent an untapped asset for both environmental restoration and economic opportunity, but their responsible use demands clear access and benefit-sharing mechanisms.

Building a shared knowledge system, reinforcing the science-policy interface, and promoting inclusive, cross-border innovation networks are essential steps forward. This policy brief calls for sustained investment in these areas to ensure that the Atlantic becomes a model of marine stewardship – resilient, equitable, and grounded in scientific understanding.

4.3.7 References

- [1] European Commission, 2025. Communication on the European Ocean Pact (COM(2025)281 of 5 June 2025).
- [2] European Commission, 2021. Communication on the Sustainable Blue Economy (COM(2021)240 of 17 May 2021).
- [3] European Commission, 2020. Communication on the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (COM(2020)380 of 20 May 2020).
- [4] European Commission, 2013. Communication on the Action Plan for a Maritime Strategy in the Atlantic Area (COM(2013)279 of 13 May 2013).
- [5] European Commission, 2025. EU Blue Economy Sectors. Available at: https://blue-economy-observatory.ec.europa.eu/eu-blue-economy-sectors_en (Accessed 16 July 2025).
- [6] United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative (UNEP FI), Sustainable Blue Finance. Available at: <https://www.unepfi.org/blue-finance/> (Accessed 16 July 2025).
- [7] UNCTAD, 2023. Trade and Environment Review 2023: Building a Sustainable and Resilient Ocean Economy Beyond 2030. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development.
- [8] European Commission, 2025. The EU Blue Economy Report 2025. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- [9] European Commission: Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, Borriello, A., Calvo Santos, A., Ghiani, M., Guillén, J. et al., 2023. The EU Blue Economy Report 2023. Publications Office of the European Union. DOI: 10.2771/7151
- [10] European Commission: Joint Research Centre, Feyen, L., Ciscar, J., Gosling, S., Ibarreta, D. et al., 2020. Climate Change Impacts and Adaptation in Europe – JRC PESETA IV Final Report. Publications Office of the European Union. DOI: 10.2760/171121
- [11] European Commission, 2024. Managing Climate Risks – Protecting People and Prosperity (COM(2024)91 final). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52024DC0091> (Accessed 16 July 2025)
- [12] European Environment Agency (EEA), 2024. European Climate Risk Assessment. Available at: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/european-climate-risk-assessment>
- [13] World Bank and United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), 2017. The Potential of the Blue Economy: Increasing Long-term Benefits of the Sustainable Use of Marine Resources for Small Island Developing States and Coastal Least Developed Countries. World Bank, Washington, DC.
- [14] Blasiak, R., Jouffray, J.-B., Wabnitz, C.C.C., Sundström, E., Österblom, H., 2018. Corporate control and global governance of marine genetic resources. *Science Advances*, 4, eaar5237. DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.aar5237
- [15] Zhivkoplías, E., Jouffray, J.-B., Dunshirn, P. et al., 2024. Growing prominence of deep-sea life in marine bioprospecting. *Nature Sustainability*, 7, 1027–1037. DOI: 10.1038/s41893-024-01392-w

[16] Flynn, K.J., Torres, R., Irigoien, X., Blackford, J.C., 2022. Plankton digital twins – a new research tool. *Journal of Plankton Research*, 44(6), 805. DOI: 10.1093/plankt/fbac042

4.4 Policy brief #4 - Clustering for Impact: Lessons learned from #AllAtlantic Cluster - Recommendations to EC REA and future HorizonEU & FP10 applicants on strategies and mechanisms for agile clustering of parallel project portfolios

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Contributing projects: Mission Atlantic, REMORA, AtlantECO, #AllAtlantic Project Managers Cluster drawing on these projects: Astral, AquaVitae, TriATLAS, iAtlantic, SUMMER, MEESO, EuroSEAS.

4.4.1 Context

“Clustering” of projects at all scales (within the same Topic, across topics under the same Societal Challenge, and across Horizon Pillars) has been an explicit priority in Framework Programmes for at least a decade. Degree of expected clustering from the beneficiaries side, has varied from unclear to highly prescriptive across Societal (and later Global) Challenges, resulting in diverse but vague interpretations of how “clustering” should be correctly put in practice.

While Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge “Secure, Clean & Efficient Energy” expected regularly beneficiaries to dedicate a WP or a Task to cluster with relevant concurrent projects at EU and national levels, Societal Challenges “Food Security” and “Climate Action” expectations were mostly unclear, or occasionally pointing to a single, specific parallel Call.

This was the case in HorizonEU Work Programmes, until WP2025 when Topic drafting started to change, in parallel to the compilation of this Policy Brief.

“We could have done much more, had we allocated a task to work together” - TechOCEANS Coordination Team

“A framework for how a portfolio ‘cluster’ should work, would be beneficial” - EuroSEAS Coordination Team

4.4.2 Opportunity

More than 64% of the “marine research” budget in 2025-2027 is locked in Topics funding more than one project. As this rises, the possibility of duplication and/or missed opportunities not detected at evaluation also

increases. As the burden on evaluation committees grows, there is a clear need for systematic solutions for parallel project funded from the same Topic, to explicitly and contractually co-deliver for impact.

Tested example cases below with potential for scalability, demonstrate how multi-project Topics offer systematic opportunities for pooling of resources from pre- to post-award stages: from co-design of proposals, co-creation with stakeholders pre- and post-award, to co-delivery and joint exploitation of results (be it towards policy or private sector). This can directly reduce likelihood of duplication of funded work, as well as reduce stakeholder fatigue as projects in the same Topic portfolio, if implemented systematically.

“Policy Briefs should represent the views of a cluster of multiple projects” - OceanICU Coordination Team

Recommendations herein are organized into those relevant for the funder, as well as for future applicants (the beneficiaries) in HorizonEU and Framework Programme 10. Where the recommendations for the applicants have been tested in funded project(s), reference is made to a specific “proposal asset” guiding applicants how to deploy and implement the recommendation in future proposals, and offer scalability.

The #AllAtlantic CLUSTER of 15+ projects, also offer a “work in progress” definition of “clustering” that may assist dialogue, and/or calibrate expectations for both funders and beneficiaries.

Definition: (work in progress, for future versions of this brief) Clustering in the context of HorizonEU Projects is more than just “name dropping” and mapping the landscape of related projects with overlapping R&D objectives. Effective clustering refers to mapping concurrent projects with similar objectives, and providing clear, specific, and dedicated tasks, with meaningful budget and partner capacities (e.g. “living bridge partners” participating in projects to be clustered) and using the full contractual flexibility embedded in the legal framework, so that the proposal/project can convincingly co-deliver joint R&D, exploitation activities, collectively reduce stakeholder fatigue, intentionally provoke evidence for early uptake of results

4.4.3 Scalable Example Cases

1. EXAMPLE Cooperation with National Science Foundation & NASA (USA)

General experience with supporting Galway Statement [1], Belem Statement [2] and #AORA [3] between 2010-2020s (via Grant Agreements like FP7-ENV-2010 & BG-08-2018-2019 [4]) consistently relied on a strategy of 1) agreeing on high-level priorities, and 2) funding “own for own” projects with the aspiration that parallel projects would cluster and collaborate in support of the high-level priorities. This type of fragmented, patchwork funding landscape imposed difficulties and frustrations for those in the community seeking specific and concrete cooperation between parallel projects with overlapping objectives. Barriers included lack of systematic access to funded projects proposals to build upon explicitly, contractual rigidity of existing funded projects, very limited contractual options to divert small funds into emerging opportunities to cluster projects together.

2. EXAMPLE RIA-type Projects

Two Sister Projects [5] funded out of H2020-LC-BG-03-2018 [6] (SUMMER and MEESO, RIAs in direct competition), were co-designed, co-drafted and co-submitted by the same research community, some of which participated in both funded projects. The “clustering” at drafting stage insured optimal fit and synergy between the two concepts, and final designs, in a way building in contingencies for “contractual rigidity” at implementation, a problem encountered frequently when clustering problems. The high level of conceptual synergies between the two proposals meant minimal duplication of work from the start, high evaluation of both proposals, and high degree of conceptual complementarity during implementation. Since the successful implementation, the case has proven relevant and topical with other parallel Topics that funded two projects at a time (e.g. TechOCEANS & Nautilus Projects in H2020 BG-07-2019-2020).

3. EXAMPLE IA-type Projects

Three Sister Projects proposed in HorizonEU MISS-2024-OCEAN-01-03 collaborated at concept design (IA's not in direct competition, same Topic objectives targeting 3 different regions). Unlike the "RIA-type Calls Case", the three sister proposals only openly shared partnerships and Exploitation Strategy, but not the details of the "Excellence" design. The case is useful for optimizing conceptual synergies, co-demonstration of solutions at high TRL [7] using embedded reserve funds, co-commercialize innovation across all regions, and reducing stakeholder fatigue on the topic of "bycatch". As the frequency of multiple project Topics increases, the opportunity for embedding conceptual synergies to underpin effective clustering is significant. Lack of applicant awareness of eligible mechanisms at their disposal, is still a major barrier to proactively mobilizing partners to co-design and co-deliver with concurrent consortia. This success story has now funded ECO-CATCH and Marine Guardian Projects, and both chair the TRAIID Bycatch Cluster (2025-2030).

4. EXAMPLE #AllAtlantic Ocean Research & Innovation Alliance

Six Sister Projects funded out of Horizon2020 BG-08-2018-2019 directly to support #AAORIA #AllAtlantic Ocean Research & Innovation Alliance, formed the initial monthly cluster at management level. The goal was clustering of SMART objectives, resources, and post-award implementation. Contractual rigidity embedded within the project design, and reluctance to use any existing mechanisms allowing for contractual flexibility, were frequently barriers to implementing specific joint research & exploitation activities across contracts.

5. EXAMPLE Clustering with Partnerships (BlueBio & Biodiversa+)

Especially on the #AAORIA priority area of "coastal resilience", HorizonEU Partnerships and Calls therein offered a promising mechanism for extending, building upon selected components of #AllAtlantic projects. In the case of BlueBio 2022 Call, #AllAtlantic projects SUMMER & MEESO were explicitly mentioned as examples to build upon. This mobilized the latter consortia to engage the rest of the community, and rapidly communicate promising areas of research, and can help visibly trace the legacy of HorizonEU project through nationally co-funded mechanisms.

The #AllAtlantic CLUSTER of project managers made sustained and repeated efforts to engage both secretariats administering BlueBIO and Biodiversa+, in order to systematically repeat the practice.

The objectives were:

- 1) offer free advice to applicants willing to build upon contract we implemented, offer pooling of resources, identify co-financing opportunities,
- 2) offer access to Grant Agreements (Part B) where those were not publicly disclosed, to accelerate direct synergies, and
- 3) offer to future Partnerships' Calls examples of projects to build upon (without influencing prioritization on Partnership Calls).

Contractual rigidity at implementation, and concerns with respect to independence of the Partnerships, i.e. entities beyond the Partnerships beneficiaries are seeking to de-nature the prioritization of Call Themes, prevented duplication of the success given above with BlueBIO Call 2022.

6. EXAMPLE Exploitation Plans in general

There is a general concern that Horizon 2020 Consortia left exploitation too late into the average 4 year projects, and even in best cases effective exploitation requires time beyond the average 4 yr project lifetime. This is also recently echoed by EC Court of Auditors Report in the context of emerging AI technology [8].

At least one Horizon 2020 Grant Agreement [9] implemented a combination of contractual flexibility through reserve funds, and an extra 12 months after the main R&D deliverable were completed. This clearly allowed the consortium to focus on exploitation alone as a project within the project, devise basic transfer pathways, and engage in the difficult task to dialogue with specific end-users (versus broad range dissemination, and one-way communication).

In addition, for many non-engineering project where the main result is new knowledge, consortia could not have devised a prescriptive and effective Exploitation Strategies 5 yrs prior to holding the tangible Key Exploitable Results (KER) in their collective hands.

Researchers gain significantly more clarity on “demonstrable benefits for specific end-users that can be causally linked to the outputs of the project [10] ” once the deliverables are finalized, and the scientific caveats fully explored.

... so what does this mean specifically for CLUSTERING in 2026-2027 funded projects? ...

“proposals should allocate sufficient resources for effective coordination, with concrete cooperation activities to be defined at a later stage” - Source: HORIZON-CL6-2025-01-BIODIV-05, first appears in draft form, Mar-Apr 2025

... and for the next Framework Programme 10 (2028-2034)? ...

“More flexibility across the budget, so Europe has the capacity to act – and react – fast when circumstances change unexpectedly or when new policy priorities need to be addressed” - Source: The 2028-2034 EU budget for a stronger Europe

4.4.4 RECOMMENDATIONS to APPLICANTS

- CLUSTER with past projects, by explicitly extending and building upon specific parts (traceable outputs/ deliverables/tasks) of past projects, instead of at overall objective level only;
- CLUSTER with specific parts (traceable outputs/deliverables/tasks) of concurrent proposals, in the interest of ad-hoc co-delivery, co-dissemination, reducing stakeholder fatigue, reducing demonstration and validation costs, and boosting collective power to reach end-users;
- CLUSTER with multiple concurrent proposals, when crafting, drafting, and proactively disseminating actionable advice & recommendations in the form of policy-relevant briefs! Stakeholder fatigue is a real problem, and single-project policy messages are a weak conduit for actionable advice;
- DEPLOY more proactive clustering instruments (e.g. reserve funds) for more targeted, specific and purposeful clustering with concurrent projects, where the joint activities deliver more than the sum of its parts;
- CLUSTER with complimentary concurrent projects, following the example of the #AllAtlantic CLUSTER of Project Managers (e.g. 30min per month, with a standing agenda on reducing duplication & stakeholder fatigue, optimizing outreach and impact) as a forum for mutual support to deliver the recommendations above, and as a collective focus on common objectives;
- Consider running distributed PROPOSAL CLINIQUEs in the closing year of the cluster of projects, to support third party applicants to national and EU R&D funds, that explicitly build on top of the research priorities (and success results!) of your projects! How many “spin-off” R&D applications you can document is an accepted KPI for the legacy of your project;
- RESERVE FUND [11] for joint PhDs is an eligible and tested mechanism, and can be deployed to mobilize 50% cofinancing by Graduate Schools within the consortium beneficiaries (easiest option) or beyond consortium (by inviting new beneficiaries in the Consortium after project start)
- RESERVE FUND for MOBILITY for ECOPs [12] is an eligible and tested mechanism, and can be an effective mechanism for resolving emerging R&D problems in the second half of the project lifetime, clustering with Sister Projects, matching with existing personal development & secondment funds within HorizonEU noneligible organizations (e.g. NOAA), capacity building with the Global South and developing countries, directly adding value to the Action.
- RESERVE FUND for EXPLOITATION (possibly combined with additional 12 months dedicated to Exploitation alone) is an eligible and tested mechanism, to systematically apply contractual flexibility,

with additional time after the main R&D deliverable are completed. Free of responsibility of the main deliverables, consortia are more likely to focus on exploitation as a project within the project.

4.4.5 RECOMMENDATIONS to FUNDERS

- OPEN PROPOSALS: in the age of AI, and in broader support of EC's commitment to Open Science, EC REA Project Officers can help raise awareness on benefits of, support and promote, publishing of Open Proposals as an optional "best practices" for RIA type Calls, in the interest of avoiding duplication, transparency, and effective clustering with other National (co-)Funding Calls in the EU and #AllAtlantic Partner Countries (while fully respecting the need for patenting, IPR & financial confidentiality). At least three precedents exist with GRECO, AtlantECO and MISSION ATLANTIC, where versions of the Description of Actions is disclosed, with consortium beneficiaries themselves deciding where is the best compromise between disclosure and confidentiality.
- CLUSTERING with relevant concurrent proposals broadly, is a more systematically embedded, default requirement in all HorizonEU Calls, with a dedicated Task for the Governance Body of the Consortium (e.g. Executive Board, Steering Group etc), or in the case of Partnerships seek to repeat BlueBIO Call 2022 example of explicitly building up named clusters of existing projects to assist traceability for REA.
- CLUSTERING with concurrent proposals in the same Call (i.e. Sister Projects), is a default expected feature of all proposals at proposal drafting stage, in the interest of co-design, co-delivery and optimizing synergies (without making proposals co-dependent).
- EC Project Officers & Financial Officers, proactively support beneficiaries to implement contractual flexibility (incl. RESERVE FUNDS, or other Grant Agreement eligible mechanisms) in their proposal design, to raise awareness on GA provisions that allow projects to be more agile.
- CONTRACTUAL FLEXIBILITY is encouraged in the official Call Text in future calls, so that applicants are more aware of eligible mechanisms (e.g. reserve funds) and embed those in early design stage.
- RESERVE FUNDS resources (amount determined by each Consortium) without an allocated cost category, are a recommended design feature of the proposal in order to empower concrete CLUSTERING activities, and add eligible contractual flexibility to deliver specific synergies with concurrent/sister projects (e.g. co-supervision of students, co-delivery, pooling of exploitation, commercialization and stakeholder outreach activities).

4.4.6 References

[1] EU, US, Canada launch Atlantic Ocean research alliance (Galway Statement)

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_13_459

[2] Belen Statement on Atlantic Research & Innovation Cooperation (Jul 2017)

https://www.aircentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/belem_statement_2017_en.pdf

[3] Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance CSA <http://www.atlanticresource.org/>

[4] All Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance Flagship, Horizon 2020 BG-08-2018-2019 Portfolio of 6 Projects over 2 years.

[5] "Sister Projects" is a frequently used reference to project funded from the same Call, whether they are in direct competition, or address the identical Call but in different regions/themes.

[6] Sustainable harvesting of marine biological resources, Horizon 2020 LC-BG-03-2018 Portfolio of 2 Projects

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/lc-bg-03-2018>

[7] Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level

[8] Special report 08/2024: EU Artificial intelligence ambition – Stronger governance and increased, more focused investment essential going forward (<https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/SR-2024-08>)

[9] Grant Agreement 862428 under H2020- BG-08-2018-2019

[10] Reed et al. 2021. Evaluating impact from research: A methodological framework, Research Policy 50,4, May 2021 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048733320302225?via%3Dihub>

[11] Proposal ASSET “Reserve Funds for Training, Mobility & Exploitation”, by #AllAtlantic Project MISSION ATLANTIC (Portfolio H2020- BG-08-2018-2019), DOI:10.5281/zenodo.735140XYZ

[12] Early Career Ocean Professional (ECOP) Network Programme, <https://www.ecopdecade.org/>

5 Conclusion

The AtlantECO policy briefs represent a strategic effort to translate cutting-edge scientific knowledge into clear, actionable recommendations that support sustainable ocean governance across the Atlantic basin. By addressing equitable research cooperation, marine genetic resources, the Sustainable Blue Economy, and effective project clustering, these briefs strengthen the science–policy interface and contribute directly to European and international marine agendas.

The project’s policy briefs reflect AtlantECO’s core values of inclusiveness, collaboration, and evidence-based decision-making. Their broad dissemination, including engagement at major international events such as the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance and the United Nations Ocean Conference, which has reinforced dialogue among policymakers, researchers, industry actors, and civil society across Europe, South America, and Africa.

Beyond the project’s lifetime, these policy briefs provide a lasting knowledge resource to inform future EU initiatives, international ocean governance frameworks, and transatlantic cooperation mechanisms. They consolidate AtlantECO’s legacy by promoting equitable partnerships, responsible innovation, and the integration of marine microbiome science into policies that safeguard the health, resilience, and sustainability of the Atlantic Ocean.